

EARTH SCIENCES

THE PURPOSE OF THE WELL LOGGING METHODS AND THE RESULTS IN THE OPERATING WELLS OF GASLI GAS FIELD IN RECENT YEARS

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Abstract

The given scientific research work describes the complex of geophysical research methods carried out in recent years in the Gazli oil and gas field, which has been in use for many years and is still producing gas and oil on an industrial scale, the stages at which they are carried out and the results obtained. It can be seen that this complex of methods is mainly used to determine the bedding interval and petrophysical parameters of the identified and currently known productive horizons, as well as to check the technical condition of the boreholes. The determination of the petrophysical parameters of the layers is carried out as a result of the interpretation of primary data obtained in field conditions using currently available modern logging devices (probes) using existing programs (Prime). As a result, the saturation characteristics of the reservoir layers are determined, and recommendations are made for the next stages, namely, the processes of checking the well wall by cementing and perforating. The sequence of these stages is explained, as well as the controversial situations that arise during the process.

Keywords: Gazli, Well Logging, Petrophysical parameters, Conductor, Saturation

INTRODUCTION

The Gazli gas and oil field is located in the Romitan district of the Bukhara region, approximately 100 km northwest of the city of Bukhara (Figure 1). It was

discovered in 1956. Its geological structure includes Jurassic, Cretaceous, Paleogene and Neogene deposits. Jurassic deposits are composed of red sandstone and clay rocks (up to 100 m thick). Deposits of all layers of the Cretaceous system are found.

Figure 1: The position of the Gazli oil and gas field (Source: OpenStreetMap)

The Gasli oil and gas field is of great importance not only in terms of gas and oil production, but also in terms of its role as a reservoir for accumulating existing gas reserves. The prospectivity of this field was determined in the middle of the 20th century and its production began in the 1960s. It has been producing hydrocarbons for half a century. In the geological section of

the Gasli rise, clay is the main stratigraphic element at depths down to the Jurassic period. Although sandstone is the main mass in some layers, the thickness of these layers is very small. However, it is precisely these small layers that can serve as a collector (the layer with a condition to hold and give hydrocarbon). Although there is stratigraphic uniformity in the existing area up to the oil

and gas layers, logging studies have been conducted in each drilled well since the field was discovered. The reason for this is the different scope of logging methods used. Because logging methods not only help identify stratigraphic units, but also reveal the depth of the productive horizon, which has changed depending on the structural state, its collector and saturation properties, the state of strata changes in tectonically active regions, and the technical conditions of the drilled well.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Structural State of the Gazli Uplift

Each anticline fold of the Gazli Uplift has its own development characteristics, but according to the time of their formation, they can be divided into only two genetic types: folds of ancient (Mesozoic) onset and sedimentary development, and folds of late (Cenozoic) onset (postsedimentary development). The local structures of the first type include, first of all, the Tosh-Kuduk anticline and, possibly, the Kurban-Ali structures. All other structures belong to the second type: Gazli, Karakir, Kukhna-Gumbas and Atbakor [1].

Based on the analysis of the history of the formation of the structures of the Gazli gas-oil region, it can be noted that the formation of gas and oil deposits here was, directly related to the manifestation of the Neogene-anthropogenic phase of the Alpine orogenesis stage, which led mainly to the final formation of individual structures and the corresponding local deformations [1]. The entire process - the formation of caps, the migration of hydrocarbon fluids and the formation of gas and oil deposits - probably represented a single genetic unity. It is clear that the deposits were formed mainly as a result of lateral and partially vertical migration from the hypsometrically lower areas of the Khorezm-Izmail deep, starting from the end of the Paleogene [2, 3]. The thick layers of Jurassic and Cretaceous terrigenous-clay sediments developed here may serve as hydrocarbon suppliers for the formation of the deposits of the Gasli oil and gas region.

Figure 2. Geological section along the Karakir-Gazli-Tash-Kuduk profile, passing through the Gazli uplift. 1- Paleozoic formations, 4- Upper Cretaceous, 5- Upper Senonian Paleogene deposits and sandstones; 6- Neogen; 9-gas fields. **Source:** E.V. Lebzin and I.V. Kushnirov, (1962).

The largest field is situated in the Gazli uplift, located in the western part of the Bukhara-Khiva region. According to the results of extensive drilling and geophysical work in this area, three fields were discovered - the Gazli oil and gas condensate field, the Tashkuduk gas field and the Mullahol oil field. The lowest reserve density was observed in the Tashkuduk field (158 million m³/km²), the maximum - in the Gazli field (1569 million m³/km²).

The geological structure of the Gazli gas and oil region includes a complex of sharply unconformable Mesozoic and Cenozoic sediments on the eroded surface of the Paleozoic folded foundation (Figure 2).

The main gas and oil layers are Cretaceous deposits, in the section of which the following sandy horizons are distinguished from bottom to top: XIII (Neocomian-Aptian), XII, XIa, XI (Albian), X, IX (Cenomanian). At the same time, in the Gazli field, industrial gas and condensate deposits are limited to horizons IX, X, XI, XIa, XII, and gas-oil deposits are limited to horizons XIII.

Current Well Logging Materials

In recent years, geophysical survey methods have been used in boreholes drilled in the research area for two main purposes: 1) To monitor the technical condition of exploitation wells up to 800 m deep for gas injection and withdrawal to the underground gas storage facility and to identify gas-retaining horizons 2) To determine the intervals of productive horizons in exploitation wells up to 1200 m deep drilled to extract hydrocarbons from the field and to provide recommendations for the perforation process by calculating petrophysical parameters.

In the first type of research, the complex of geophysical methods mainly consists of GK (gamma logging), NGK (neutron gamma logging), 2NNKt (neutron neutron logging) and AK (acoustic logging). Although the methods used do not provide complete information about the formation parameters, they allow for an estimate of the results by comparing and contrasting them with the results of previous research in neighboring wells. Also, the technical condition of the well walls is assessed (through Acoustic Logging).

The complex of geophysical methods in the second type of research includes - Caverometry, Inclino-etry, Radioactive methods (GK, NGK), Induction logging (IK), Acoustic logging (AK), Lateral logging (BK), Resistimetry and other additional methods (Figure 3). In the above methods, recordings are made at a

speed of 300-800 m/h. With the help of this complex of methods, starting from the assessment of the technical condition of the well, the separation of productive horizons, the nature of saturation, the effective layer thickness (through microprobes) and other petrophysical parameters of the layers are determined.

Figure 3: Sample plot of the well logging diagram in the Gazli area and the range of parameter changes. This diagram shows the borehole diameter (*D*), the electric resistivity (*BK*) and conductivity (*IK*) of the rocks in the well walls, the natural (*GK*) and secondary radioactivity (*HGK*), the natural electric field (*IC*) and the electric field in the induced polarization (*KC*).

Source: From the database of the UzbekGeofizika

RESULTS

As previously mentioned (Figure 2), the results show that the terigenous rocks of the Lower and Middle Cretaceous deposits act as reservoirs as gas-bearing

rocks. Therefore, in the range of 500-800 m (see Figure 4), the reservoir layers are distinguished as gas-saturated intervals in the logging diagrams.

Figure 4. A plan of the productive (gas) horizons and saturation properties of the Gazli deposit, separated by a complex of Logging methods.

Source: Based on materials from the UzbekGeofizika

In the section of the Gazli deposit, the natural radioactivity of rocks has a relatively high value due to the clay content and is 4-15 $\mu\text{P/h}$. Resistivity indicators vary in the range of 10-90 Ohms, depending on the nature and degree of saturation of the layers (Figures 4, 5).

Since the Gazli rise is located on the Bukhara tectonic step of the Bukhara-Khiva oil and gas region, the main productive horizons are located in the Cretaceous

period. The entire Cretaceous section is mainly composed of terrigenous structures - clay, siltstone and sandstone. 8 sets (horizons) of permeable reservoir rocks are distinguished in the section of the Cretaceous layers. They consist of siltstones and sandstones, separated from each other by impermeable rocks - clay, clayey siltstones. In production practice, such packages of permeable rocks are called productive horizons.

Figure 5. A plan of the productive (gas) horizons and the nature of the saturation in the Gazli field, separated by a complex of Logging methods.

Source: Based on materials from the UzbekGeofizika materials

Horizons XIV and XIII are located in the red layers of the Neocomian, horizons XIV and XIII are located in the gray terrigenous-clayey layers of the Apt deposits, horizon XI is located in the Albian deposits, horizons X and IX are located in the Cenomanian deposits, horizon VIII is located in the Turonian deposits, and horizon VII is located in the Senonian deposits [4].

As can be seen in Figure 6, the productive horizons currently being produced by oil and gas correspond to the terrigenous deposits of the Lower Cretaceous, and these horizons are interpreted as several small-interval reservoirs and gas-saturated rocks in layers deeper than 1000 m. The total thickness of these layers is around 10m, and they are still producing hydrocarbon reserves on an industrial scale.

CONCLUSION

The study conducted in the Gazli oil and gas field underscores the crucial role of advanced well logging methods in optimizing the exploration and extraction processes in mature hydrocarbon fields. Through the use of geophysical techniques such as gamma logging, neutron gamma logging, acoustic logging, and resistivity measurements, significant insights have been gained

into the technical conditions of boreholes, the petrophysical properties of reservoir layers, and the productive horizons.

The findings highlight the effectiveness of these methods in identifying gas-saturated intervals within the Cretaceous deposits, ensuring the efficient recovery of hydrocarbons from the field. Moreover, the study also illustrates the geological complexity of the Gazli uplift, with productive horizons characterized by terrigenous reservoirs and stratigraphic variations.

This comprehensive approach not only contributes to extending the field's operational life but also demonstrates the value of integrating modern geophysical tools in maximizing the potential of established oil and gas fields. Future work should continue focusing on refining these techniques and addressing challenges associated with reservoir heterogeneity and evolving production requirements.

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